

METICOS

A Platform for Monitoring and Prediction of Social Impact and Acceptability of Modern Border Control Technology

Deliverable D5.2

Technology Acceptance User Survey Results

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Abstract:	<p>Deliverable D5.2 provides an overview of the Technology Acceptance Modeling (TAM) data collection activities that took place during Iteration 1 of the METICOS project. To this end, it describes the goals, concept and design of the data collection surveys performed and provides a descriptive analysis of the resulting data.</p> <p>This deliverable mainly consists of two parts: the first part discusses the pilot survey, while the second part focuses on the main large-scale survey. Both Iteration 1 surveys targeted EU citizens in their role as travelers.</p>
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Terms and abbreviations

BC	Border Control
BCP	Border Control Point
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EES	European Union Entry/Exit System
SBC	Smart Border Control
SEM	Structural Equation Modeling
SOTA	State of the Art
TAM	Technology Acceptance Model/Modelling
TCN	Third-Country Nationals
TCNVE	Third-Country Nationals Visa Exempt
TCNVH	Third-Country Nationals Visa Holders
UTAUT	Unified theory of acceptance and use of technology
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
PEOU	Perceived Ease of Use
BI	Behavioral Intention
IDV	Individualism versus Collectivism
NN	Neural Network
PTE	Previous travels
EEOU	Expected ease of use
EIOP	Exp. Impact on privacy
EIHW	Exp. impact on personal health
PE	Performance expectancy
TIPT	Trust in particular technology
EC	Expected convenience
BITU	Behavioural intention to use
TIA	Trust in BCA
GIT	General interest in technology
CO	Collectivism
UA	Uncertainty avoidance
PD	Power distance
MA	Masculinity
LTO	Long-term orientation
DISC	Former discrimination experience

Executive Summary

Deliverable D5.2 provides an overview of the Technology Acceptance Modeling (TAM) data collection activities that took place during Iteration 1 of the METICOS project. To this end, it describes the goals, concept and design of the data collection surveys performed and provides a descriptive analysis of the resulting data.

This deliverable consists of two main parts: the first part discusses the pilot survey of project Iteration 1, while the second part focuses on the main survey. Both surveys targeted EU citizens in their role as travelers.

Finally, conclusions and findings from the results are derived, particularly as regards upcoming data collection and modeling activities in work package WP5. Among those, key findings and conclusions are:

- Size and quality of the dataset resulting from the main survey were found to be sufficient for TAM Modeling.
- TAM factors are well represented by their underlying items and correlations among factors follow plausible, explainable patterns.
- Issues such as occasionally observed small effect sizes and scoring differences between user groups as well as the fact that fully balancing of age groups could not be fully realized, have to be taken into account in future analysis and modeling.

1 Introduction

1.1 About this deliverable

Deliverable D5.1 provides an overview of the Technology Acceptance Modelling (TAM) data collection that took place in the first Iteration of WP5 Task 5.2. Building on the results of D5.1 (state of art analysis, identification of existing datasets, etc.), it describes methods and processes used for empirical data collection that took place in the form of online surveys. Furthermore, the processing of the results data and descriptive statistical analysis of the resulting datasets are presented. The resulting datasets are hosted by the data storage infrastructure built in task T5.3 and form the basis for the TAM modelling activities in task T5.4.

1.2 Document structure

After the introduction, Section 2 presents the general approach and method used for data collection in T5.2 Iteration 1. Then, the concept and results of the pilot study are discussed in Section 3, followed by the presentation of the main study and its results dataset in Section 4. Finally, Section 5 summarizes findings and conclusions and discusses resulting implications for the METICOS project, particularly as regards forthcoming activities in work package WP5.

2 General Approach and Methods Used

2.1 Goals and Requirements for data collection

In general, the primary objective of data collection in METICOS WP5 is **to enable the creation of datasets that allow accurate modeling the acceptance of SBC (Smart Border Control) technology** by the stakeholder groups (travelers, border control staff) targeted by the project. Furthermore, the data should provide insights in acceptance-related factors like user attitudes and characteristics.

To this end, the data collection should fulfill the following general criteria:

- ecological validity,
- representativeness of samples,
- sufficiently high number of data points (to ensure statistical significance as well as proper training and validation of acceptance models),
- completeness and correctness of records,
- data privacy and security,
- absence of bias¹,
- relevant SBC technologies addressed, and
- relevant stakeholder acceptance aspects and driving factors addressed.

As regards the latter, beyond addressing already known acceptance factors such as privacy, ease of use, etc., also taking into account the potential impact of user diversity as well as experienced discrimination is deemed essential (cf. deliverable D5.1). Their study can have a significant impact on the ability to recognize power relations and hierarchies and to respond to the varying needs and vulnerabilities and consequently, the reduction of inequalities and protection of human rights of people crossing borders. In this context, also cultural dimensions should be investigated in order to better understand modulators in border control technology experience and acceptance across different countries and national origins.

However, as already identified in deliverable D5.1, due to the general lack of TAM datasets matching the targeted technologies and application context, the main source of METICOS TAM modeling data can only result from the data collection activities performed within task T5.2.

Technology acceptance of SBC is also a matter of ethical acceptability and corresponding requirements for conducting empirical research. One of the most important factors in this context is the understanding that the target group of such technology – travelers - is heterogeneous. In this context questions are raised in relation to diversity dimensions, such as how acceptance is shown in relation of different age groups, whether there are differences shown in relation to the gender of the participants or also in relation to cultural dimensions, e.g. of national cultural values (see also D5.1).

This is reflected in the respect of diversity aspects in the designed questionnaire as well as the possibilities to reach participants and grant the access to take part in the survey. Additionally, SBC and acceptance is a matter of trust. The issue and regulation of data protection also contributes to the feeling of security in dealing with a technology as a variable of technology acceptance. From an ethical point of view, personal data has to be protected in the context of such surveys. Taking those factors in account this study aimed at integrating the travelers' perspective with an EU wide traveler survey. After pretesting the method roughly 8.000 questionnaires were answered for METICOS in the main traveler survey.

¹ For a comprehensive taxonomy of biases see <https://doi.org/10.6028/NIST.SP.1270-draft>.

2.2 General approach and methods used

As outlined in the METICOS project plan and description of work, the first iteration of data collection and technology acceptance modeling focuses on the perspective of EU citizens in their role as travelers. To this end, a large-scale questionnaire study (a common approach in technology acceptance modeling) was conceived and implemented. This “main” questionnaire survey campaign (N=8000, eight EU countries) was preceded by a smaller pilot study (N=400, one EU country, see Table 1⁽⁰⁰⁰⁾) with the purpose of risk management in terms of trialing the developed questionnaire at small scale first before committing significant resources.

Using an online questionnaire as research method has a lot of advantages because it saves resources such as time and money. It is also possible to reach a large number of potential participants in different countries in a short time. From an ethical perspective, challenges arise when conducting online research. This starts with the technology competence and availability of devices as requirement. In this context socio-economic status, education as well as age become crucial factors of accessibility and therefore are to be taken into account as limitations of surveys conducted. When it comes to the research instrument itself and the data collected ethical aspects are particularly with respect to privacy, confidentiality and informed consent of research participants. To address the need for an equitable approach, it is also necessary to communicate transparency about who the study is originating from and what its purpose is [1].

Therefore, a research framework was designed to address these critical aspects and enable a balanced sampling. One part of this process was to use an inclusive design of the questionnaire and the visualizations. To ensure transparency, reference was made to the project and as introducing part of the questionnaire and the possibility was also given to contact the project partner carrying out the study if there were and further questions or complaints.

In terms of responsibilities for the implementation of the study, the questionnaire was mainly developed by the AIT, reviewed by JOAFG and the visualizations for the technology stimuli were delivered by VILABS. The assignment of the survey agency as well as the coordination for necessary adaptations for the study was taken over by JOAFG. Furthermore, the review of the study and the structure of the questionnaire with regard to ethical concerns was handled and improved by consulting VUB and implementing the input.

The different parts of the TAM online panel survey session follow the typical structure of a questionnaire-based online campaign (see Table 1). Noteworthy are Steps 5 and 6, where a randomly selected SBC technology stimulus (text, graphics) is presented to the respondent, who subsequently provides his/her opinions and feedback by answering a number of acceptance factors related questions.

Table 1: Stages of the Traveler TAM Online Questionnaire Session.

Step
1 Screener
2 Intro
3 Informed Consent
4 Background and Demographics
5 Stimulus presentation of SBC technology
6 Acceptance questions
7 Debriefing

To ensure a representative sample, quotas for gender and age were specified and the equal distribution of the questionnaires among the technologies were determined in advance. The limitation that could lead to an unbalanced distribution stems from relatively lower technology adoption and literacy, often associated with older age, resulting in lower accessibility to online research tools for the 65 + age group [2]. In addition, the frequency of travel was checked to see if the participants at least had made one border crossing of an EU external border (EU external borders to non-EU borders and within the EU) between 2015 and 2019.

Table 2: Key parameters of the two traveler-focused TAM online survey campaigns.

Parameter	Pilot Survey	Main Survey
Start	September 2021	December 2021
Survey period	2 weeks	1 – 2 months
Languages	German	As required by populations in target countries (see below)
Sample	n=400	n=8000
Target group	Traveler	Traveler
Target countries	Austria	8 EU countries: Austria, Belgium, France, Greece/Cyprus, Estonia, Norway, Romania, Sweden
Screeners		
Travel frequency	Travelled to or from an EU country between 2015 and 2019- if not fulfilled, then no inclusion/drop-out	Travelled to or from an EU country between 2015 and 2019 - if not fulfilled, then no inclusion/drop-out
Quotas targeted (not coupled)		
Gender	Equal share of men and women	Equal share of men and women
Age	Equal distribution in the categories: 18-39 years, 40-64 years, 65-80 years	Equal distribution in the categories: 18-39 years, 40-64 years, 65-80 years (with limitations)
Other	Two technologies with 200 respondents each	In each country, the same number of questionnaires should be collected for each stimulus

Based on the literature review results and consideration of project priorities (cf. D5.1), a TAM model was drafted that featured a long list of relevant factors that could be included in the SBC technology acceptance questionnaire campaigns, each one falling into one of the following three categories: technology related-aspects, user characteristics, and cultural orientation (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: METICOS TAM model draft.

However, since a questionnaire covering all potential variables of interest would be too extensive and laborious to be reliably answered by online panelists, a pruning step based on prioritization was performed in the following way: in the context of online workshops, all long-listed factors were prioritized all METICOS WP5 partners by means of importance scores. Imposing a time budget of max. 15 minutes for answering all questionnaire items as a limit, the highest scoring factors were ultimately included in the prospective SBC TAM questionnaire (see Table 3).

Table 3: Acceptance and cultural orientation factors as addressed by the SBC Traveler TAM questionnaire.

Technology-related	Expected ease of use Expected impact on privacy Expected impact on personal health & well-being Performance expectancy Trust in particular technology Expected convenience
User characteristics	Trust in border control authority Previous travel experience Previous SBC experience General interest in technology Demographics (age, gender, ...)
Cultural orientation	Collectivism Uncertainty avoidance Power distance Masculinity Future orientation

The TAM survey was designed to indirectly measure 16 latent variables (also termed “factors” in this document), by using multiple questions covering a given latent variable. Table 4 shows each variable with its corresponding abbreviation as used in further analysis. The value of each latent variable was calculated by simple averaging of the scores its corresponding observed variables (i.e., rating items).

Table 4: Abbreviations of latent variables in the surveys.

PTE	Previous travels
EEOU	Expected ease of use
EIOP	Exp. Impact on privacy
EIHW	Exp. impact on personal health
PE	Performance expectancy
TIPT	Trust in particular technology
EC	Expected convenience
BITU	Behavioural intention to use
TIA	Trust in BCA
GIT	General interest in technology
CO	Collectivism
UA	Uncertainty avoidance
PD	Power distance
MA	Masculinity
LTO	Long-term orientation
DISC	Former discrimination experience

The questionnaire was iteratively improved throughout a series of cognitive pre-tests with potential respondents, conducted by AIT in Vienna. The purpose of such pre-tests is to identify limitations regarding the content and formal aspects (wording, grammar, etc.) of an instrument to avoid systematic biases and unintended answering behavior later in the Pilot and the Main Survey. For this a preliminary version of the questionnaire consisting of the text elements for information and instruction, the stimulus material (E-Gate, fingerprint) and a set of 51 items was presented separately to four respondents (see Table 5). Two respondents were researchers at AIT who had been unfamiliar with the project or the purpose of the survey. On the other side they were highly experienced in the development and application of interrogation techniques within HCI research. Two others were external users recruited by AIT without any relation to the conducted research.

Table 5: Respondents that took part in the cognitive pre-tests.

Respondent ID	gender	age	type	duration
1	w	24	E-Gate	5min25sec
2	w	32	E-Gate	6min28sec
3	m	21	E-Gate	7min31sec
4	m	49	E-Gate	13min16sec

All four sessions followed the same procedure: after a short introduction of the task context, respondents were asked to fill the paper-pencil questionnaire quietly on their own, while the facilitator took time and notes. Next, they were invited to read again through the text of the questionnaire from the beginning while applying the “thinking aloud” technique. By this means problematic formulations and comprehension issues were identified and discussed.

Beside minor wording adjustments in 11 questions, major issues concerned questions addressing the factors Trust in particular technology (TIPT) and Trust in border control authority (TIA) (see Table 5). Context information about which EU countries exactly should be able to process personal data, respectively which borders are addressed, was added. Furthermore, the time frame in questions about previous travel behavior (PTE, PSBC) was narrowed to the time span between 2015 and 2019 in order to explicitly address personal travel routines independent from travel experiences in the Covid-19 era.

Table 6: Revision of items Trust in particular technology (TIPT) and Trust in border control authority (TIA)

Question ID	Preliminary text	Revision
TIPT_2	Ich vertraue darauf, dass das Grenzkontrollpersonal, das E-Gate richtig benutzt.	Ich vertraue darauf, dass das E-Gate bei der Benutzung richtig funktioniert und das Bedienungspersonal, dieses richtig handhabt.
TIPT_2	I trust the border control personnel to use the e-gate properly.	I trust that the e-gate will function properly when used and that the operators will handle it correctly.
TIA_1	Ich vertraue den Grenzkontrollbehörden.	I trust the border control authorities.
TIA_2	Ich vertraue den Grenzkontrollbehörden an den EU-Außengrenzen.	I trust the border control authorities at the EU's external borders.

Confusion was reported by two respondents regarding the E-Gate stimulus material itself. Without any context information about the concrete border control technology used in this stimulus condition, respondents stressed the risk that future survey respondents might associate specific technologies or make speculations about a concrete technology in use, which might affect and blur the answers.

Overall, based on the feedback from cognitive pre-tests we concluded that all questions can be kept for the questionnaire, with no question excluded from the set. As regards economy and survey conduction duration, we conclude from pre-tests that the actual amounts of questions seem to be reasonable in terms of mental and cognitive workload for respondents.

3 Pilot Traveler Survey

3.1 Study Goals

The main purpose of the pilot study was **risk management**: before committing significant resources (here: questionnaire translation, participant recruitment and incentives), a prior test run helps to check whether the study design and setup produces meaningful data or whether there are problems like confusing questionnaire items, misleading stimulus presentation, wrong sample size, etc. To this end, a pilot study was conducted in a single country, using a limited set of stimuli.

3.2 Study Design, Methods and Materials

The aim of the pilot survey was to test our study approach via two technologies (one macro level technology = e-Gate, one micro level technology = fingerprint reader) evaluated by 400 online survey participants from Austria.

The two online questionnaires for the pilot study were structured as follows:

- 1) Screening questions: For balancing (e.g., similar amount of male and female respondents, balanced age groups, etc.) potential participants had to fill out screening questions about their previous travel experience, their age and their gender. These questions were used to decide if the following questions were presented to the participant, or if the survey was over for the participant.
- 2) General information: Next, the purpose of the study, basic information about the research project, contact information and instructions how to fill the questionnaire out are presented.
- 3) Introduction of the stimulus: Next, one of the two border gate technologies is described via text and via a visualization:
 - a. Text for e-Gate: “An E-Gate is a system that enables automated border crossing. In this process, data for proof of identity, border control records or authorizations for border crossing can be queried.” (see Figure 2)
 - b. Text for fingerprint scanner: “A fingerprint scanner is a sensor for scanning a finger to generate a digital image of the fingerprint. This can be used to retrieve data for proof of identity, border control records or authorizations to cross the border.” (see Figure 3)
- 4) Questions about perception and expectations regarding the border technology: Next, several questions items about expected ease of use, expected impact on privacy, expected impact on personal health, performance expectancy, trust in particular technology, expected convenience, expected convenience have to be answered via 7-point Likert-scales, e.g., “the fingerprint scanner is a trustworthy technology” has to be answered via a scale ranging from 1 (=strongly disagree) to 7 (=strongly agree).
- 5) Questions about previous travel experiences, attitudes and demographic information: Next, several questions have to be answered about trust in border control authorities, previous smart border control experience, former discrimination experience, discrimination expectancy, general interest in technology, collectivism, uncertainty avoidance, power distance, masculinity, long-term orientation, education, nationality and place of birth.

Figure 2: Illustration of e-Gate interaction.

Figure 3: Illustration of fingerprint sensor interaction.

The complete questionnaires are listed in the annex of this deliverable.

Recruiting for the online survey has been done by a panel host, a professional agency owning a pool of registered panelists, who get a sort of incentive for participating. By creating an account, the panelists confirm a GDPR-conform informed consent to participate in surveys at the panel provider, which carries out the questionnaire in cooperation with the agency contracted by JOAFG. This ensured that people were responding on a volunteer base. Furthermore, the sample plan included the equal distribution of participants in the regions of Austria. This is why the ZIP Code and place of residence was part of the questionnaire. Before the data sets were submitted for analysis as password-protected files, which were screened for information that could compromise participant privacy.

3.3 Pilot Survey Results

3.3.1 Dataset Characteristics

The pilot traveler survey's dataset consists of 409 filled out questionnaires. After data consistency check, there was not any filtering of the dataset needed. There were 205 male and 204 female responders. As specified, responses were evenly distributed across two technologies, with 204 samples for E-Gate and 205 for fingerprint sensor. Figure 4 shows the distribution of responses between different age groups. The majority of the travelers were in the range from 40 to 64 years of age, while 65-80 age group was the smallest. Consequently, we asked the online panel agency to manage for a better age balance in the main survey. The percentage distribution of participants among the specified age groups appears to be related to category size rather than equal representation.

Figure 4: Number of respondents for each technology, gender and age group in pilot study.

3.3.2 Dataset Analysis

To analyze correlation patterns between the different acceptance factors, the Spearman Rank-order correlation matrix was computed (see Figure 5). Results show that core TAM factors (EEOU, PE, TIPT, EC, BITU, TIA) are strongly positively correlated (SROCC ≥ 0.4) with each other. Also, EIOP and EIHW are visibly correlated with aforementioned factors, albeit negatively due to their reversed polarity. Factors related to cultural orientation (CO, UA, PD, MA, LTO) are only weakly correlated to each other, except the PD and MA pair, with SROCC 0.47. These observations are within expectations and are in line with results of prior studies using Hofstede’s framework (cf. [3], [4]), as well as previous results on individual cultural values [5]. Note, that among the cultural background factors, only UA (uncertainty avoidance) shows medium to strong correlation with TAM factors. All in all, the observed correlations appear to be plausible and are in line with existing research.

Spearman correlation matrix

Figure 5: Spearman correlation matrix for the latent variables addressed by the pilot study.

To illustrate the patterns of ratings and scores along different data splits and panel segmentations, we are going to present a representative analysis of a selected factor – Behavioural Intention to Use (BITU). BITU plays a major role in technology acceptance modeling, as it is the target variable that expresses to which extent a person is likely to accept and actually use the technology under scrutiny. Figure 6 presents BITU scores split by to technology and gender. While there are visible differences between given two technologies (albeit at small effect sizes), there are no visible differences between ratings from different gender. Figure 7 depicts scores by technology and age group. Here, an influence of age is at least observable for the E-Gate. Note, that scores from the oldest age group might be skewed because of the overall lower number of datapoints.

To explore significance of age, gender and technology on other latent variables we performed ANOVA tests. Highly significant impact ($P \leq 0.001$) of technology was observed on EIH, PE, EC and BITU variables, highly significant impact of gender ($P \leq 0.001$) was observed only for GIT and MA variables – which was expected result confirming validity of the results. Age influence had significant impact ($P \leq 0.05$) only for EEOU, EIOP, EC and UA variables.

Figure 6: Raincloud plots of BITU scores split by gender and technology. Each column consists of a traditional box-plot overlaid with a strip-plot, a probability density curve and a blue marker indicating the mean and error-bars (95% CI) of the distribution.

Figure 7: BITU scores by age group and technology.

We conducted a confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) to test our measuring model, i.e., we check if our observed variables (=questionnaire items) can be used to determine the latent variables, here also labeled as factors (e.g., three expected ease of use question items are combined to determine the factor EEOU). Hence, a chi-square test was conducted to check if our measurement model fits our empirical data. The following results were achieved:

Table 4: Results of Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA)

Result	Thresholds [6] [7]	Interpretation
Chi-squared test statistic: $\chi^2=1565,703$, $df=797$, $p=0.000$	-	Measurement model approved
Comparative Fit Index (CFI) = 0.946	> 0.9 (acceptable fit); >0.95 (good fit)	Measurement model approved
Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI) = 0.936	> 0.9	Measurement model approved
Root Mean Square Error of Approximation RMSEA = 0.049	< 0.06	Measurement model approved
Standardized Root Mean Square Residual SRMR = 0.048	< 0.11	Measurement model approved

Based on the results of the CFA our measurement model can be approved.

3.4 Conclusions from Pilot Traveler Survey

The pilot results dataset was found to be well-balanced across technologies and gender. Age groups were found to be imbalanced to some extent, an issue, which was also communicated to the executing survey agency.

The correlation matrix shows plausible patterns of correlations between the different TAM factors that are explainable and exhibit sufficient degree of significance.

The analysis of resulting TAM factors (with our presentation in this deliverable focusing on BITU – Behavioral Intention to Use) shows that resulting scores are well distributed across the scale (albeit with visible scale-end effects) and match common patterns of rating behavior. Also, a number of significant (but not large) differences could be found between the two SBC technologies (fingerprint scanner, E-Gate) and user segmentations (by gender, age, etc.), indicating that the target figure of N=200 per country per technology represents a reasonable trade-off between costs (arising from panel size) and significance of results. Surprisingly, gender differences were found to be fairly small compared to other segmentations (age, etc.). We expect that in results of the main survey, gender differences are likely to be more pronounced because of the overall larger N and the wider range of countries involved.

The CFA shows that the different variables are well-represented by the respective underlying questionnaire items.

Nonetheless, a few items were improved in terms of wording, and one was exchanged: for the factor masculinity (MA), one item did not relate to the other questions on masculinity, as shown by intercorrelation matrix ("Men usually solve problems with logical analysis; women usually solve problems with intuition.", MA_2). The item might address different aspects of masculinity than the others. Or, as literature shows, as masculinity scales are often developed for the work-context, a question measuring gender differences such as MA_2 might relate less to the other questions which rather focus on work-value differences [5]. However, towards providing a more congruent set of items addressing the MA masculinity factor for acceptance modeling in the main survey, we chose a different

item instead as an alternative (“It is preferable to have a man in high level position rather than a woman.”), based on its high factor loading [5] (see also Section 4.2).

All in all, the results of the pilot study suggest, that the chosen approach is able to fulfil the stated goals, that measurements are sensitive and deliver valid results. Therefore, we decided to apply our method also to the main survey, given a few minor modifications.

4 Main Traveler Survey

4.1 Study Goals

As already mentioned before, the goal of the main survey is to **produce a sufficiently large body of valid, representative modeling** data that can be used to develop TAMs that can reliably predict and explain technology acceptance of the selected set of five SBC technologies from a traveler perspective. To this end, a large-scale online survey (N \geq 8000) was performed in eight EU-countries.

4.2 Study Design, Methods & Materials

The results of the pilot study show, that only small adaptations in the test design were necessary before the larger main survey was executed (adaptations are described below). The structure of the final main survey was similar compared to the pilot study, five online questionnaires were used to cover the following border gate technologies: fingerprint scanner, e-Gate, passport scanner, face recognition and 3D faces on the move recognition.

The five online questionnaires for the main study were structured as follows:

- 1) **Screening questions:** For balancing (e.g., similar amount of male and female respondents, balanced age groups, etc.) potential participants had to fill out screening questions about their age, place of residence and zip code and their gender. These questions were used to decide if the following questions were presented to the participant, or if the survey was over for the participant. In contrast to the pilot study, additional information was collected about place of residence and zip code.
- 2) **General information:** Next, the purpose of the study, basic information about the research project, contact information and instructions how to fill the questionnaire out are presented.
- 3) **Previous travel experience:** Next, detailed information about previous travel experiences is collected. In contrast to the pilot study, the question texts were more detailed. For example, instead of asking “How often did you - on average - cross EU-borders annually before 2020?”, the question text was “How often did you - on average - cross EU-borders annually before 2020? Outward and return journeys are to be counted separately.”
- 4) **Introduction of the stimulus:** Next, one of the five border gate technologies is described via text and via a visualization:
 - a. Text for e-Gate: “An E-Gate is a system that enables automated border crossing. In this process, data for proof of identity, border control records or authorizations for border crossing can be queried.”
 - b. Text for fingerprint scanner: “A fingerprint sensor is a sensor for scanning a finger to generate a digital image of the fingerprint. This can be used to retrieve data for proof of identity, border control records or authorizations to cross the border.”
 - c. Text for passport scanner: “A passport reader captures the document to be inspected, read essential information from the captured image and forwards this information to the processing computer system, so that the travel documents can be verified with specific databases.”
 - d. Text for Face Recognition: “Facial recognition is a way of identifying or confirming an individual’s identity on behalf of the person’s face. The camera detects, locates and captures the image of a face to identify the facial landmarks that are key to

distinguishing different faces. Then, these facial landmarks are compared against the information which is digitally stored in the passport or in an external database.” (See Figure 8.)

- e. Text for 3D Faces-on-the-move recognition “A 3D face scanner is a system for detecting or confirming an individual's identity on behalf of the person's face. A traveler has to pass through a designated corridor, where during the walk-through, his or her face is automatically scanned via several cameras mounted at different angles. The entire verification process is performed without the person having to stop. At the exit of the corridor, a border guard is informed about the result of the identity check via tablet.”
- 5) Questions about perception and expectations regarding the border technology: Next, several questions items about expected ease of use, expected impact on privacy, expected impact on personal health, performance expectancy, trust in particular technology, expected convenience, expected convenience have to be answered via 7-point Likert-scales, e.g., “the fingerprint scanner is a trustworthy technology” has to be answered via a scale ranging from 1 (=strongly disagree) to 7 (=strongly agree).
 - 6) Questions about previous travel experiences, attitudes and demographic information: Next, several questions have to be answered about trust in border control authorities, previous smart border control experience, former discrimination experience, discrimination expectancy, general interest in technology, collectivism, uncertainty avoidance, power distance, masculinity, long-term orientation, education, nationality and place of birth. In contrast to the pilot study, the question text “Men usually solve problems with logical analysis; women usually solve problems with intuition.” was changed to “It is preferable to have a man in high level position rather than a woman.”

Figure 8: Illustration of face recognition.

The complete questionnaire of the main study is listed in the annex of this deliverable.

Besides the German questionnaires for the data collection in Austria the questionnaires were provided in English as basis for the translations into the other languages (Estonian, French, Greek, Norwegian, Romanian, and Swedish). The sample plan for each country was defined by the regions of the respective country and except Estonia, which is not divided into regions. The following sample limitations of the main survey, which were clarified prior to commissioning, should be mentioned here. For Greece and Cyprus, the survey was limited to the age groups up to 65 years, because the older age group over 65 years cannot be reached to a sufficient extent with online surveys. Since there was only a French translation of the questionnaire, the sample from Belgium derives from the French speaking part of the country, Wallonia. Regarding data protection and quality management for the main survey, the commissioned agency worked exclusively with partners who are themselves ISO-certified (20252:2019) and thus meet the same quality standards and GDPR conformity. After completion of the survey the collected data of all countries was transmitted by the agency in one password protected data set.

4.3 Main Survey Results

4.3.1 Data Preprocessing and Analysis Dataset Characteristics

The main traveler survey’s raw dataset consists of 8010 filled out questionnaires. There were 3899 male and 4058 female responders. Moreover, 53 panelists answered the question about their gender as neither men nor women but chose the option diverse. As specified, responses were evenly distributed across technologies, with around 1600 samples for each technology – 3D face scanner (1604), e-Gate (1599), fingerprint sensor (1605), face recognition (1598) and passport scanner (1604).

The dataset was filtered, using rating variance or suspicious answers or gender information. As the filter, low variance in Likert’s scale rating was used – eliminating all samples with variance lower than 0.1. Because of the modelling requirements, we also removed travelers with no gender info. Additionally, we further split dataset into two categories – travelers with more than 150 travels to or from EU in the period of 2015-2019 and travelers with higher number of travels in that period. Due to very low variance in ratings, 296 results were eliminated, 53 results did not have information about the gender. The group of travelers with high number of travels consists of 26 people – for further analysis, we call this group as frequent flyers.

Figure 9 shows details of the final analysis dataset which consists of 7639 datapoints (i.e., survey responses)². After having applied all aforementioned filtering steps, the analysis dataset remains evenly distributed among different technologies, countries, and gender – each country, technology and gender is represented by nearly 100 results. Note, that the age group 65-80 years is consistently smaller than age groups 18-39 and 40-64 in nearly all countries and completely missing in Greece. The panel hosting agency explains this imbalance with the fact that this age group is significantly harder to recruit for online surveys. This general problem in terms of lack of availability of older panelists is a well-known shortcoming of online surveys (cf. [8]). The resulting imbalance between age groups must be considered in subsequent inferential analysis and modeling stages.

Figure 9: Number of respondents for each technology, country, gender and age group.

² Note, that different filters are not mutually exclusive, e.g., low variance of ratings might also be accompanied with no gender information, or suspiciously high number of travels in the period from 2015-2019

Representation of education can be seen in Figure 10. Absolute majority of the travelers did have minimum high school education or university degree of some sort. Analysis of the travelers’ reported nationality is highly related to the country where the survey was performed - Figure 11 shows, that most respondents reported the same nationality as the country in which the survey took place.

Figure 10: Dataset split by country of survey and respondent education.

Figure 11: Dataset split by country of survey and respondent nationality.

Comparing main study cohorts with results from the pilot study – visible in Figure 4, we have a similar number of results for each category of technology and gender, where age group 65-80 years has similar proportions in the main study as in the pilot study.

4.3.2 Correlation analysis

To analyze correlation patterns between the different acceptance factors, the Spearman Rank-order correlation matrix was computed (see Figure 12). As already observed in the pilot study, almost all stronger correlations (SROCC ≥ 0.4) are positive (except for EIOP and EIHW). As expected, most core TAM core factors (EEOU, PE, TIPT, EC, BITU, TIA)³ are strongly correlated with each other. Factors like TIPT, PE and EIOP are strongly correlated with BITU, which confirms the results of similar studies (cf. Lancelot et al. [9], Kasim et al. [10] and Kim et al. [11]).

Factors related to cultural orientation (CO, UA, PD, MA, LTO) are only weakly correlated with each other, except the PD \leftrightarrow MA pair. These observations are within expectations and are in line with results of prior studies using Hofstede’s framework (cf. [3], [4]), as well as previous results on individual cultural values [5]. Note, that among the cultural background factors, only UA (uncertainty avoidance) shows medium to strong correlation with TAM factors.

Figure 12: Spearman Correlation Matrix of the different acceptance factors. Red colours indicate positive, blue colours negative correlation. Note: factor EIOP and EIHW has reverse polarity.

³ For an explanation of the different factor acronyms please refer to **Error! Reference source not found.**

4.3.3 Factor: Behavioral Intention to Use

The TAM models to be developed for the ETAP module heavily rely on having a clear picture to which extent users accept a certain SBC technology and what the main drivers are. In our studies, this is represented by target variable Behavioral Intention to Use (BITU). Because of its representativeness and importance as direct proxy for acceptance, the subsequent analysis is going to focus on BITU.

Figure 13 below shows the distribution of BITU scores for the different technologies addressed. As visible, the scores for each technology follow a (skewed) normal distribution with peaks in the range of 5 to 6 (x-axis). Given the fact, that 7-point Likert scales were used for scoring the underlying items, these distributions suggest that in general, participants reported a high propensity to accept all presented SBC technologies, with passport scanner scoring highest and 3D face recognition scoring lowest on average.

Figure 13: Distribution (probability densities) of BITU scores by SBC technology.

Figure 14 below shows the impact of gender on BITU scores⁴. Surprisingly, there is no statistical difference between male and female scores, except for the case of the 3D Face Recognition technology where a slight difference can be observed (4.88 m vs. 4.63 f), which might be explained by the fact that 3D Face Recognition represents the most advanced technology, challenging participants perception and interpretation of the respective stimulus in the survey. Still, this result suggests that overall, gender has no noteworthy influence on acceptance of the five different SBC technologies tested.

This result is further surprising as regards a previous assumption on specific traveling circumstances, respectively that more women travel with children than men. Here, we would have expected significant differences in TAM in relation with women encountering certain issues when proceeding with SBC technologies together with small children. However, in-depth analyses are yet to be effectuated on the influence of traveling circumstances (alone vs. with children) and frequencies on TAM factors.

⁴ Note, that due the very low number of datapoints, data for gender “diverse” is omitted here.

Figure 14: BITU by Technology and Gender.

Figure 15: BITU by Technology and Age Group.

4.3.4 Cultural Orientation and Experienced Discrimination

Looking at the ratings for cultural orientation, the overall sample in the main survey is found to be relatively high in uncertainty avoidance (UA), with collectivism (CO) following a nearly normal distribution. Furthermore, the sample is dominated by individuals with low power distance (PD) and very low masculinity (MA) cultural values, which overall seems plausible in view of previously postulated cultural dimensions for EU countries [12], considering Western countries as rather individualistic, uncertainty avoiding and with lower power distance and masculinity compared to Eastern cultures. On a country level, the ratings on national cultural values are overall above average in UA and LTO, while they remain considerably low in PD and MA in all countries. Through this first screening data plausibility can be assumed across countries with no indication for compromised data. Differences (e.g., higher ratings in UA for Romania, lower LTO for Sweden) seem reasonable considering individuals socialized in different national cultures with varying tolerances (e.g., for uncertainty). However, as statements on geographical level lack empirical evidence and validity, they need to be handled with care. Thus, for our TAM modelling, we rely on careful interpretation of individual national cultural values. As previously identified as relevant moderators of TAM factors [5] [13], UA and CO show strong correlations. As for LTO, our data does not confirm previous results from literature, which however is not conclusive in this regard.

UA (uncertainty avoidance) shows medium to strong correlation with TAM factors, especially expected convenience (EC). Interestingly and against previous findings on cross-cultural differences in technology adoption (Erumban & de Jong, 2020), respondents with a high score on uncertainty avoidance expect high convenience with using SBCs compared to people who show low-level UA.

Referring to previous assumptions on the moderating effect of national cultural variables on technology-related beliefs and behaviors (Srite & Karahann, 2006) we found medium correlation between general interest in technology (GIT) and selected cultural orientation variables (CO, UA, LTO). In our sample greater self-reported interest in technology came along with higher ratings on collectivistic attitude (CO), tendency of avoidance risk and uncertainty (UA) as well as higher long-term orientation (LTO). Although previous results showed opposite relationships (greater individualistic orientation relates to greater GIT) as our data reveals, CO might be further investigated for some modulating effect in the relationship between TAM factors in line with literature.

Figure 16: Uncertainty avoidance (UA) by country.

Figure 17: Power distance (PD) by country.

Figure 18: Masculinity (MA) by country.

Figure 19: Long-term orientation (LTO) by country.

As for the items addressing discrimination (DISC2), survey data reveals medium positive correlation between TAM factors (PE, TIPT, EC, BITU) and high ratings on expectations concerning the future potential contribution of SBC against discrimination in a border control situation. Similarly, low expectations are related to lower scores for aforementioned TAM factors.

4.4 Conclusions from Main Traveler Survey

The analysis of the results data of the main survey suggests, that the goal of obtaining a sufficiently sized, representative body of TAM modeling was obtained for the selected SBC technologies and countries. For the majority of the questionnaire items, we observed sufficient levels of variance and the resulting factors exhibit a matrix of weak to strong correlations, indicating patterns of relationships that are plausible and in line with existing research. Differences between resulting score averages are statistically significant in many cases, indicating that our measurement is sensitive.

In the main survey aspects of cultural orientation were assessed through a selection of items addressing national cultural values i.e., uncertainty avoidance (UA), collectivism (CO), power distance (PD), masculinity (MA) and long-term orientation (LTO). The screening of results show strong correlation of UA and medium correlation of LTO on TAM factors. Although the strong correlation between PD and MA underlines the plausibility in the data, lack of relationship between TAM factors and PD and MA reveal that these two factors might not be suitable indicators for cultural orientation within the context of cross EU countries investigation.

We also observed some surprising outcomes: for example, for the majority of the TAM factors (including BITU) and technologies, we could not detect any difference by gender, in contrast to other segmentations such as by age or by country. This suggests a broad acceptance among both men and women, which may be explained by the usefulness of the control or the obligatory nature of a border crossing by using the technology as a necessity. In this context, it would be interesting to examine previous border crossing experiences in more detail.

Nonetheless, the resulting analysis also suggests that the dataset is not perfect. For example, due to practical circumstances, age groups could not be balanced as desired, particularly as regards participation of panelists aged 65+. Since as stated before this age segment is not that well reachable

with an online panel, an alternative data collection method could be considered. Furthermore, the share of certain user segments (e.g., age groups, education level groups) deviates considerably in certain countries. These issues need to be taken into account in upcoming inferential analysis and modeling steps (e.g. by stratification) in order to avoid representation bias and confounding.

5 Conclusions and Implications for the METICOS Project

This deliverable has presented an overview of the Technology Acceptance Modelling (TAM) data collection activities that took place in the first iteration of WP5 Task 5.2. To this end, methods and processes used for empirical data collection that took place in the form of online surveys (a pilot and a large-scale main study) were described. Furthermore, the processing of the results data and descriptive statistical analysis of the resulting datasets were presented.

The analysis of the results data analysis shows that our method delivered trustworthy, albeit not perfect datasets that can be used for subsequent TAM modeling activities which will take place in task T5.4. Furthermore, the lessons learned from the presented traveler focused survey will be helpful when designing and implementing the border control staff focused surveys in Iteration 2 of task 5.2.

6 References

- [1] B. Hanganu, I. S. Manoiilescu, and B. G. Ioan, "Ethical Challenges in Online Research," *J. Intercult. Manag. Ethics*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 17–24, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.35478/jime.2021.3.03.
- [2] B. Klimova and P. Poulouva, "Older People and Technology Acceptance," in *Human Aspects of IT for the Aged Population. Acceptance, Communication and Participation*, Cham, 2018, pp. 85–94. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-92034-4_7.
- [3] A. Maleki and M. de Jong, "A Proposal for Clustering the Dimensions of National Culture," *Cross-Cult. Res.*, vol. 48, no. 2, pp. 107–143, May 2014, doi: 10.1177/1069397113510268.
- [4] X. Li, T. J. Hess, A. L. McNab, and Y. Yu, "Culture and acceptance of global web sites: a cross-country study of the effects of national cultural values on acceptance of a personal web portal," vol. 40, no. 4, p. 26, 2009.
- [5] Srite and Karahanna, "The Role of Espoused National Cultural Values in Technology Acceptance," *MIS Q.*, vol. 30, no. 3, p. 679, 2006, doi: 10.2307/25148745.
- [6] P. M. Bentler and D. G. Bonett, "Significance tests and goodness of fit in the analysis of covariance structures," *Psychol. Bull.*, vol. 88, no. 3, pp. 588–606, 1980, doi: 10.1037/0033-2909.88.3.588.
- [7] M. R. S. Maulana and P. Rufaidah, "Co-creation of Small-medium Enterprises," *Procedia - Soc. Behav. Sci.*, vol. 115, pp. 198–206, Feb. 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.02.428.
- [8] M. L. Remillard, K. M. Mazor, S. L. Cutrona, J. H. Gurwitz, and J. Tjia, "Systematic Review of the Use of Online Questionnaires among the Geriatric Population," *J. Am. Geriatr. Soc.*, vol. 62, no. 4, pp. 696–705, Apr. 2014, doi: 10.1111/jgs.12747.
- [9] C. Lancelot Miltgen, A. Popovič, and T. Oliveira, "Determinants of end-user acceptance of biometrics: Integrating the 'Big 3' of technology acceptance with privacy context," *Decis. Support Syst.*, vol. 56, pp. 103–114, Dec. 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.dss.2013.05.010.
- [10] K. O. Kasim, S. R. Winter, D. Liu, J. R. Keebler, and T. B. Spence, "Passengers' perceptions on the use of biometrics at airports: A statistical model of the extended theory of planned behavior," *Technol. Soc.*, vol. 67, p. 101806, 2021, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2021.101806>.
- [11] E. S. Kim *et al.*, "Implementation and Effects of an Information Technology–Based Intervention to Support Speech and Language Therapy Among Stroke Patients With Aphasia: Protocol for a Virtual Randomized Controlled Trial," *JMIR Res. Protoc.*, vol. 10, no. 7, p. e30621, Jul. 2021, doi: 10.2196/30621.
- [12] G. Hofstede, *Culture's Consequences*. Newbury Park, CA: Sage Publications, 1984.
- [13] J. Lu, J. Wei, C. Yu, and C. Liu, "How do post-usage factors and espoused cultural values impact mobile payment continuation?," *Behav. Inf. Technol.*, vol. 36, no. 2, pp. 140–164, Feb. 2017, doi: 10.1080/0144929X.2016.1208773.

7 Annexes

7.1 Annex 1: Additional Results Charts (Main Survey)

Figure 20: Scatter plot spearman correlation matrix for main study factors. Upper-right cells display correlation coefficients (asterisks denote significance of correlation), lower-left cells are scatter plots with non-linear fittings, cells on the diagonal show histograms of each factor.

Figure 21: Distribution of Likert ratings for the three items constituting Behavioural Intention to Use (BITU).

